

FATIGUE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES AT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to develop an understanding of the fatigue life of composites (in this case, Cytec IM7/5250-4 carbon fiber-reinforced bismaleimide) at room temperature and in liquid nitrogen (-196°C). Cyclic life data from multi-directional laminate specimens are presented. In addition, the quantification of transverse cracks in multidirectional laminates is examined. Emphasis is placed on the initiation and growth of transverse cracks, since their presence may increase the permeation of cryogenic liquids through the laminates.

To conduct the tests, specialized grips and an insulated stainless steel tub were designed and fabricated. After installation, liquid nitrogen was allowed to flow into the tub and completely submerge the specimen. Once filled, the temperature was allowed to equilibrate in the LN₂ for approximately 15 minutes. For testing at both room temperature and in liquid nitrogen, power laws seem reasonable to fit the stress – cycles to failure (S-N) curve. Transverse microcracking in each of the plies was quantified at fixed intervals under both static and fatigue loading.

KEYWORDS: fatigue, composites, bismaleimide, cryogenic, microcracking

INTRODUCTION

Trade studies of next-generation space launch vehicles include both expendable and reusable concepts. These studies have highlighted the vehicle dry weight as a critical parameter in achieving desired payload to orbit. The use of structural composite liquid oxygen and liquid hydrogen tanks, lines, ducts, and valves for this purpose has been proposed. The present study was undertaken to assess the fatigue life of a carbon/bismaleimide polymer matrix composite material under cryogenic conditions. In actual service, the composites could possibly be exposed to cryogenic liquid oxygen (-183°C) and liquid hydrogen (-253°C). Because, in the reusable concept, the cryogenic tank would also be subjected to high heating upon vehicle re-entry, a higher use temperature material (carbon fiber-reinforced bismaleimide) was chosen for this study. The use of a higher temperature material would allow a reduction in the amount of thermal protective materials required to insulate the composite materials from excessive temperatures.

TEST SPECIMENS AND PROCEDURE

Panels of eight-ply $[0/90/45/-45]_s$ carbon fiber-reinforced bismaleimide, Cytec IM7/5250-4 were fabricated, autoclave processed, and postcured according to the established manufacturer's procedures. Specimen dimensions used were width = 1.5 cm and length = 5 cm (gage section). Extreme care was used to ensure adequate but not excessive clamp-up pressure and a high degree of specimen alignment, to prevent bending and other stresses that may lead to premature microcracking or failure. The test alignment fixture and sample test specimen are shown in Figure 1.

The test procedure first required clamping the end grips to each specimen while in the alignment fixture. Then, the specimen/end grip assembly was removed from the alignment fixture and installed (via end pins) in the servohydraulic load frame. A custom-fabricated insulated stainless steel tub surrounded the assembly (Figure 2). After installation, liquid nitrogen, LN_2 , was allowed to flow into the tub and completely submerge the specimen. Once filled, the assembly temperature was allowed to equilibrate in the LN_2 for approximately 15 minutes. Subsequently, the specimens were cycled at a rate of 10 Hz at $R = 0.1$, until final failure. Several of the specimens (whose edges were polished before testing) were removed from the load frame at fixed intervals to document the amount of microcracking observed. They were then returned to the load frame to continue cycling. In addition, limited quasi-static tests were conducted to examine the development of microcracks as a function of applied load. In these tests, the specimens were loaded until acoustic emission transducers detected the onset of transverse cracking. Next, the specimens were removed from the load frame and the edges examined. They were then returned to the load frame, and further loaded another fixed increment.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results for the statically loaded specimens are presented in Figures 3-6. Figure 3 is indicative of the type of cracking observed. The figure clearly shows the uncracked, outer 0° plies at the top and bottom of the figure. Adjacent to them are the 90° plies, followed by the $+45^\circ$ plies, and finally the -45° plies, adjacent to each other (the centerline of the laminate lies between this block of -45° plies). Cracks in the 90° plies did not always extend directly into the 45° plies (although this was sometimes observed). It was common that, as the crack density increased, if cracks in adjacent plies were offset slightly, cracks initiated in the region between plies to form delaminations. It is the linking of the transverse ply cracks by delaminations that provide the final pathway for leakage. Studies of the final development of delamination damage are ongoing and the topic of future works.

Results for the 90° transverse ply cracking is shown in Figure 4. The plot shows transverse crack density versus the applied load. Note that, for both laminates, the initial cracks both occurred at about 350 MPa of applied load (confirmed by the detection of acoustic emission). Increases in transverse crack density occurred in the room temperature laminate at a slightly higher rate than the laminate tested in liquid nitrogen. This may be due to the fact that, although the 90° plies in liquid nitrogen are subject to higher internal residual stress, the ply strength in liquid nitrogen is higher than that at room temperature. Cracks in both the room temperature and LN_2 tests appear to reach a saturation level (crack density leveling off as a function of applied stress) before final laminate failure.

The results for transverse crack formation in the $+45$ and -45 degree plies are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. The degree of cracking in the 45° ply was not as severe in the 90° ply. Similarly, cracks in the -45° ply were fewer still. In both the $+45$ and -45 plies, cracking was more severe in the cryogenic temperature tests. In no instances in the $+45$ or -45 plies did cracks reach a saturation state. The differences between the crack density in the $+45$ and -45 plies would not be predicted via classical

laminates theory. Full three dimensional stress analysis to examine the complete stress states are underway.

Results from the cyclically loaded fatigue specimens are given in Figures 7–11. Figure 7 shows the stress amplitude dependence on the number of cycles to failure. It can be seen that, for stress amplitudes greater than 550 MPa, testing at room temperature produced longer lives. Below that level, the cryogenic fatigue results appear to produce higher cycles to failure than the room temperature tests. In addition, for the room temperature tests, it appears the S-N ‘life’ curve starts from the static results (cycle to failure = 1) as initially fairly flat, then transitions to a linear drop. The liquid nitrogen results appear to show a quick drop from the static results, then also transition into a linear regime. The linear regimes are enhanced in Figure 8. Power-law curve fits through these portions of the curve appear to be fairly reasonable.

Note that one room temperature and one liquid nitrogen data point in Figure 8 are labeled “microcrack studies.” These specimens (cycled at a peak load of 586 MPa) were removed from the load frame at fixed cycle intervals and examined in an optical microscope. As with the static tests discussed previously, cracks were counted in all eight of the plies. The results for the 90° plies are given in Figure 9. The liquid nitrogen specimen clearly reached crack saturation much sooner than the room temperature case. In addition, the liquid nitrogen specimen reaches a crack saturation level (28 cracks/cm in one of the plies) similar to the static case (32 cracks/cm as shown in Figure 4). The room temperature results are even closer, at 34 cracks/cm in both the static and cyclic cases.

Figure 10 depicts the transverse crack density counts in the 45° ply of the cyclically loaded specimens. In comparison to Figure 5 (45° static results), we observe that, first, the liquid nitrogen specimens produce more cracks in both the static and fatigue cases. Secondly, the LN₂ fatigue case has crack counts that are almost fully saturated at failure, while at room temperature (also cyclic) it appears this is probably the case. This is unlike the static results, in which crack saturation has not been reached for either temperature. The –45° comparisons are given in Figure 11 (fatigue) and Figure 6 (static). We observe that in both cases the LN specimens have higher crack counts. Also, in no case are the cracks fully saturated (although possibly approaching it in the room temperature fatigue case). We also note in Figure 11 (fatigue), as in the static case, the reduced crack density when compared to the crack density in the +45° plies.

CONCLUSIONS

Laminates of Cytec IM7/5250-4 carbon fiber-reinforced bismaleimide composite material, [0/90/+45/-45]_s, were tested in fatigue at room temperature and at –196°C in liquid nitrogen. A specialized alignment fixture and test protocol were developed for the –196°C testing. Both static and fatigue tests were conducted. The resulting S-N curves show a major portion of the fatigue lives can generally be given by power laws. The temperature giving the maximum fatigue life depended upon the peak cyclic stress level. Transverse crack density counts for both static and cyclically loaded specimens were taken by removing specimens at fixed intervals and examining their edges. The results showed, in general, higher crack densities in the liquid nitrogen than at room temperature. The crack density saturated in the 90° plies in both the static and fatigue cases. Cracking density was less in the +45 plies (static and fatigue) than that observed in the 90° plies, and lower still in the –45° plies (static and fatigue). Studies underway include an investigation of the transverse crack linking via delamination, as well as three dimensional stress analysis.

Figure 1. Test specimen and alignment fixture.

Figure 2. Specimen submerged in liquid nitrogen during test.

Figure 3. Example edge showing laminate cross-section and transverse cracks.

Figure 4. Crack density in the 90° ply as a function of applied quasi-static loading.

Figure 5. Crack density in the +45° ply as a function of applied quasi-static loading.

Figure 6. Crack density in the -45° ply as a function of applied quasi-static loading.

Figure 7. Stress Amplitude versus number of cycles to failure.

Figure 8. Stress Amplitude versus number of cycles to failure, depicting linear portion of the curve fits.

Figure 9. Crack density in the 90° ply as a function of number of applied fatigue cycles.

Figure 10. Crack density in the +45° ply as a function of number of applied fatigue cycles.

Figure 11. Crack density in the -45° ply as a function of number of applied fatigue cycles.